

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-3, JUNE 2025

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ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Oriental and Occidental World in the Short Stories of Somerset Maugham

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Article History: Submitted-31/05/2025, Revised-18/06/2025, Accepted-22/06/2025, Published-30/06/2025.

Abstract:

Somerset Maugham was a globe trotter who loved seeing different parts of the world, different people and their culture. He visited different countries, both occidental and oriental, in search of raw material as his most of the stories grew from his travels and fascinated with the South Sea Islands. On all his travels to distant lands, he was not only a pleasure seeker who enjoyed comfort and luxury and who felt free from obligations, what he actually looking for were 'the characters' of his stories. He says, "what excited me was to meet one person after another who was new to me". (The Summing Up 193).

Keywords: occidental, oriental, stories, travels, obligations.

Somerset Maugham's wide acquaintance with varied geographical and cultural background develops a catholicity of vision in him. He knows very well how to use people in different situations with varied backgrounds. He does not copy original, in fact he takes what he wants from them. Through his journey from east to west, he acknowledged that people are too elusive, too shadowy to be copied. He spreads his spell with the same well lubricated assurance as the most cunning angler does his line, and the quarry stays hooked. And in this task, his experiences to oriental and occidental locales incorporate to attract the readers. He

tries to gain an insight into the contradictory motivations in man. On one hand, he saw the Europeans who take a native or half-caste (belongs to both races) woman into their houses and eventually succumb to the darker race, on the other hand, the white woman, who is certain of her husband's physical relations with a native woman, collapses and returns to England.

He was exhilarated at the mysterious charm of nature in the Eastern islands. His stories are full of myriad description of natural background that attracted Europeans. In capturing its beauty and ugliness, its topicality and typicality, Maugham has revealed a deep perception. He took Malayan locale as an ideal background for his fiction. In this oriental setting, Maugham enjoys heightening the contrast between the wonderful serene backdrops of lagoon, hibiscus blossom, coconut trees and scented romantic dusk, and the bitter tragedies. In fact, what interested Maugham was the life of the Europeans in these parts of the world. There were mainly British, French and Dutch colonies. Most of the eastern countries at that time were under the European rule. He says in the Preface to a volume of his collected short stories-

“When I first visited those countries the lives the white men and their wives led there differed but little from what they had been twenty five years before. They got home leave once in five years. They had besides a few weeks leave every year. If they lived where the climate was exhausting they sought the fresh air for some hill station not too far away; if like some of the government servants, they lived where they might not see another white man for weeks on end, they went to Singapore so that they might consort for a time with their kind. The Times when it arrived at a station up country, in Borneo for instance, was six weeks old, and they were lucky if they received the Singapore paper in a fortnight. (Vol.IV)

Maugham was interested in finding out what actually circumstances made of a man in those areas. Living in an alien country and more often an isolated life under a typical climate made man behave in a manner different from what they would have done in ordinary circumstances on their homelands. Sometimes it is the serenity and calm of nature that fascinates those Europeans who never think to return back to their native lands. In the story, ‘The Fall of Edward Barnard’, the writer gives the beautiful description of the beauty of island. Edward, the hero of the story said that it was only in Tahiti that he found real happiness and learnt what was important for him: “I never knew I had a soul till I found it here.”(79) Edward plans to remain on Tahiti for the rest of his life. In the short story, ‘Red’, Neilson also gains the physical relaxation as he comes to Samoa suffering from tuberculosis and soon “the open air, the equable temperature, the rest, the simple fare, began to have an unexpected effect on his health.....and on a sudden he saw the possibility that he might live”. Gruyter in the story ‘The vessel of wrath’ is a typical Maugham character, kind and tolerant. He enjoys life on his remote island and all the advantage and conveniences which come with his position.

If to some Europeans, the Orient has brought happiness and provided them a meaning of life, on the other hand, to the hero of short story ‘The Pool’, it brings misery and ruin. He is intoxicated to see the beauty of the pool where he often goes to bathe, but, at last, he has to suffer death in the same pool.

Maugham has also dealt with the problem of the half castes or Eurasians. They led a torn life. They could neither join the whites nor make themselves live with the natives. They had to suffer inferior complex. Even those among them who have attained high positions are presented as unhappy creatures at odds with themselves. On the other hand, Maugham also presents the problem of the white father and his relation with his half-caste children. As Lawson in the story ‘The Pool’, cannot overcome his disappointment about the predominance of native traits in his children. When the first one was born he had been hopeful that the

characteristics of the white race would be stronger “He had not expected it to be so dark. After all it had but a fourth part of native blood, and there was no reason really why it should not look just like an English baby; but huddled together in his arms, sallow, its head covered already with black hair, with huge black eyes, it might have been a native child”.(143) The same disappointment is felt by Guy in ‘The force of circumstance’ about his three children by a native girl. When his English wife Doris learns of his former liaison and the children resulting from it, she is filled with physical revulsion. Although she realizes that loneliness and the lack of any white society had driven him into the arms of the native woman, she is unable any longer to love her husband.

In Maugham’s far eastern stories one group deserve our special attention- missionaries. Maugham was a keen observer of the missionaries. Although both Catholics and Protestants appear in his narratives, he never discusses the relative values of these religions. In presenting their representatives, he always tries to maintain his strictly neutral attitude. Apparently the individual members of Catholic faith whom the author has met in the East belonged to a better than the Protestants. He found the examples of courage, sacrifice and deep religious faith in the catholic missionaries. In Rain, the role of Davidson as a missionary is very adventurous. He performs his duty very well in the areas where there are no facilities to go and cure properly the troubles of the natives. Sometimes his orders are very strict as a dictator over simple people. In the story ‘Honolulu’, the author deals with the descendants of missionaries, many of whom have become quite wealthy. One of the characters asks the narrator –

Do you know your Bible ?

‘Fairly’, I answered.

There is a text which says: The fathers have eaten sour grapes and the children's teeth are set on edge. I guess it runs differently in Honolulu. The fathers brought Christianity to the Kanaka and the children jumped his land (90).

The native kings have the missionaries land as a mark of esteem, and soon they developed this into profitable commercial enterprise. In "P&O" Maugham makes it clear that many of these protestant missionaries are disappointed if they are denied the comfortable life of modern conveniences.

In Maugham's stories, there is no evidence that the English tried to influence the thinking of the natives neither in the culture nor in their way of life. Of course, they introduced a new political system to the country including the separation of powers and the administrative structure. In 'The Letter', Maugham describes the English lawyer Mr. Joyce who works in Singapore and the legal system there resembles the one modern Europe which leads to the conclusion that it has been brought in by the Europeans. In Mr. Joyce case all the persons involved are English but naturally the European law applied also for the natives as in 'The Outstation'. At the end of the story , when Mr Cooper has obviously been killed by his Malaya servant, Warburton sends for the supposed murderer because "Justice must be done". The English also improved the life standard of the population regarding the medical care and the level of education. They provided the hospitals and schools which, however, were mainly used by Europeans. In Maugham's stories, there is no indication that the natives went to school to learn English but the opposite is depicted :” I spoke to them, but they didn't know a word of English (The Force of Circumstance 45)

The influence of native people was limited to the cultural sector which included the language and their way of life. As it is shown in Maugham's stories, most people that had stayed in the colonies for a long time understood and spoke the native language well. Even the women who had come to the East after marrying a colonel tried to learn the language fast to

communicate with their native servants. In 'The Force of Circumstance', Doris who lately arrived in the Federated Malay States is studying the Malay language in her free time. But the English men did not only gain practical knowledge like the native tongue but also emotional impressions. Colonel Warburton in 'The Outstation' experienced the kindness of the natives and changed from a superficial English snob to an understanding ruler that doesn't like at the color but at the character of somebody. Men like him helped a lot reduce the prejudices against colored people. Although they did not actively fight against racism they contributed to the changes in public attitudes towards foreigners because their meeting with the natives was of positive nature and this is what they passed.

In the story 'P&O', Maugham describes the spiritual habits of the Asian people that upset most Europeans. They were confused whether the gods of the natives existed. Gallagher is on his way from Malaya to his home country England when he suddenly gets hiccups which he cannot stop again. Some passengers on the ship are rumoring that a spell has been casted on him by his Malay mistress which is denied by others that don't believe in witchcraft. But when Mr. Gallagher cannot be cured, everybody on the ship starts panicking and in the end they are helpless to save his life. The story shows the disagreement of the English about the existence of native religious power. They were not sure whether things like spells and curses could affect them which made it easy for the native to influence them.

In Maugham's stories, one finds mostly Malays as houseboys and servants but Chinese men as clerks and cooks. Malays are described as obedient but passionate and revengeful when one provokes them. It is said of the Chinese that they are sharper and cleverer. It is important to know that the natives were poor families even sold their daughters to the Englishmen to get some money-and mostly illiterate because the education level was very low. To earn money they had to work in the houses or on the field of the white men although the working conditions were bad. Maugham embellished the situation of the servant in his stories. In 'The

Force of Circumstance’, the duties of the Malay houseboys are to carry water, to serve food for their master or to keep the house in order. They do their work in such a patient and relaxed way that we get the impression they just helping Guy because they like him and not that it is their job or that they are forced to do it. The only story that describes the hard life of the servants is ‘The Outstation’ where Cooper wants his houseboy to do all the work alone after the other servants have run away because of bad treatment. But in the same story the opposite is shown too. The servants of Colonel Warburton are not afraid of their master once he has even saved one of the boys’ lives but they obey him almost without argument and they rarely say their own opinion. In general, the Malay servants were able to live a life free from worries if their employer was understanding and fair. In the opposite, the Chinese clerk that works in the office of the lawyer Mr. Joyce is well educated and has a great influence on his chief. In ‘The Letter’, Maugham describes the Chinese people as outwardly friendly but deceitful inwards. The Chinese Clerk who works for Mr. Joyce seems to be loyal and helpful but if we take a close look we find out that he is doing everything to his own favor he is telling his employer about the existence of a letter that will incriminate his client who is supposed to be innocent. The only way for the layer to prevent the publication of the letter is to get hold of it and to do so he has to pay an enormous amount of money to the owner of the letter, a Chinese woman. This story shows the cohesion of the Chinese people and their mental superiority over the English.

On the contrary, in Europe Maugham has never found these contradictions in such an obvious form as in exotic regions, for, European civilization he believes, exercises such a powerful influence upon man that he is unconditionally subjected to it. He says, “In civilized communities, men’s idiosyncrasies are mitigated by the necessity of conforming to certain rules of behavior. Culture is a mask that hides their faces. Here people showed themselves

bare.”(The Summing Up) . When asked by an American writer, Robert Van Gelder about his returning to the English scene for characters and background, he replied-

In England, you know, civilization goes fairly deep and it is an old civilization. This makes for an apparent sameness in the people- one must go through many layers to discover what it is that sets each man apart, to discover the unique and the natural man. Every man is unique, of course, but the strangeness that makes a man a story, the oddity within him, is not easy to find in a man who wears his civilization thickly. (K.W.Jonas 101)

Maugham’s stories like ‘The Kite’, ‘Jane’, Lord Mountdrago’, ‘ The Creative Impulse’, ‘The Alien Corn’, ‘Luncheon’, ‘Promise’, ‘The Unconquered’, and ‘The Human Element’ have European background.

In these stories, Maugham effectively presents the pompous life of ostentatious people who enjoy the modern life. They used to see the outward beauty of persons. As in the story ‘The Kite’, Mrs. Sunbury, the most mannered and aristocratic lady, always tries to make her son just like her. Mrs. Albert Forrester in ‘The Creative Impulse’ has the snob for her parties organized on every Sunday with eight guests which is according to her is the perfect number of general conversation. In ‘The Social Sense’ MacDonald’s parties are toss-up. They suffer from the delusion that if they asked six persons to dine with them who has nothing in the world to say to one another the party would be failure, but if they multiply it by three and ask eighteen it must be a success. ‘The Alien Corn’ is study of a Jewish family of great wealth who are trying to escape from all the tremendous implications of their racial inheritance and turn themselves into the perfect, the complete, English Country family. Maugham introduces one of his great snobs, Ferdy Rabenstein. Ferdy is a sophisticated cosmopolitan snob, who has nearly 7000 words before we come to the story, which gives us a glimpse of a rich and cultivated Jewish family in the nineties or a little later. Lord Mountdrago is a story of the

ablest politician in the Conservative party. He is a brilliant debater and his gift of repartee is celebrated. He is a fearful snob.

Maugham deliberately refers special traits of orient and occidental localities where he enjoyed and somewhat suffered unique traditions and manners. Whereas he finds contradictions in eastern background, on the contrary he observes the similarity in the mannerism of western society. Here we find a specific blend of fact and fiction as first he prepares the base of reality and then constructs each story with garnished creativity. Whatever he, it is with special purpose- to entertain the general mass with his delighting hues of oriental and occidental background.

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